

CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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The Republic of Uzbekistan's Constitution, laws governing the environment, and popular demands for environmental safety all mention Uzbekistan's ecological status. This political-legal statement defines the reasonable use of natural resources and environmental protection in the context of our nation's natural environment.

Our constitution has reinforced the major tenets of our state's environmental policy, as well as the laws and regulations pertaining to individuals' and legal entities' rights and obligations with regard to the environment.

The revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved by 90.21% of voters in the national referendum that took place on April 30, 2023. Voting in support of 156 demonstrates that it reflects our people's dreams and desires for the creation of New Uzbekistan¹.

At this crucial juncture in the history of national statehood, the recently amended Constitution established the political and legal framework for New Uzbekistan's strategy and established the priorities for the state's and society's future growth.

The referendum was a reliable expression of the unity and solidarity of our great multinational nation and its determination to build a sovereign, democratic, legal, social, and secular state.

The Constitution, in particular, introduced the concepts of social justice and solidarity, strengthened the constitutional foundations that provide entirely new

¹ <https://www.insonhuquqlari.uz/oz/news/m11846>

mechanisms for the protection of human rights and freedoms, and defined the new strategic goal of state building as the creation of a social state.

The President, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Oliy Majlis have their respective powers redistributed, with consideration given to the principle of separation of powers and the contemporary notion of the system of mutual constraint and balancing of interests. It was intended to create a new type of state power organization based on the delegation of authority to local governors and people's deputation councils.

The notion of "for the dignity of man," which serves as the cornerstone of the reforms enacted in our nation, and the philosophy of "man-society-State," which serves as the primary tenet of the current reforms, are, in reality, profoundly ingrained in the language of our Constitution. Human dignity, honor, and pride are paramount in every aspect of life in the new Uzbekistan. A large portion of the standards outlined in the amended Constitution speak to the fundamental freedoms, rights, and obligations of individuals and citizens.

The constitution's expression of legal and environmental norms is one of them. It should be mentioned that because of the drying up of the Aral Sea, changes in the global climate, and the growing urgency of ecological safety, environmental challenges are represented in our Basic Law.

In the 49th revision of our Constitution "Everyone shall have the right to a favorable environment, reliable information about its condition.

The State shall create conditions for the implementation of public control in the field of urban planning activities in order to ensure the environmental rights of citizens and prevention of harmful environmental impact.

Draft urban planning documents shall be subject to public discussion in the manner prescribed by law.

The State, under the principle of sustainable development, shall implement measures to improve, restore and protect the environment, maintain ecological balance.

The State shall take measures to protect and restore the ecological system, social and economic development of the Aral Sea region” the norm has been strengthened.

This article's significance stems primarily from people' fundamental rights to live in natural settings that are suitable for their needs and from their ability to learn about the condition of the environment and the changes that are occurring in it. explains.

The identification of these rights guarantees the incorporation of the international agreements that the Republic of Uzbekistan has ratified into our domestic laws.

Second, it establishes the procedures by which state agencies will carry out significant environmental rights. Public control over the implementation of laws, programs, and urban planning documents adopted in the field of ecology is particularly important. The public should also be informed about draft construction documents pertaining to housing, social structures, and industrial facilities, and public hearings and expert testimony should be held, comprises measurements.

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